

EXPERIMENTS TOWARDS THE SYNTHESIS OF PHYSIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE LACTONES. PART I. *cyclopentyl-* AND *cyclohexylsuccinic* ACIDS.
RESOLUTION OF *dl-cyclopentyl-*SUCCINIC ACID.*

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The syntheses of α -ring substituted succinic acids, such as α -*cyclopentyl*-, α -*cyclohexylsuccinic* acid, required in connection with the synthesis of physiologically active lactones, are described. Some preliminary experiments towards the conversion of ethyl α -*cyclopentylsuccinate* into the requisite lactonic structure have been made, and β -aldehyde β -*cyclopentylpropionic* acid has been obtained. *dl-cyclopentylsuccinic* acid has been resolved into its optical antipodes.

Correlating the structural features of the cardiac aglucones with their physiological property, it can be inferred that the latter effect is mainly due to the presence of a $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ -unsaturated γ -lactone ring in the molecule. The aetiocholane ring structure perhaps serves the purpose of a convenient framework for the attachment of the lactone group. It was considered of interest to verify this hypothesis by the synthesis of lactones of relevant structure carrying in the first instance simpler rings like *cyclopentane* and *cyclohexane* in place of the aetiocholane ring. The following scheme was drawn up for achieving the object in view.

(R = ****cyclopentyl**, ****cyclohexyl** ; R' = H, Et).

The last two stages follow the postulative mechanism of Windaus (*Wiss. Math. Phy. Kl., Göttingen*, 1835, 70) in his derivation of the lactone structure of the cardiac aglucones from the side chain of *norcholanic* acid.

In the present paper is described the synthesis of (I, R = *cyclopentyl*, *cyclohexyl*), (II, R = *cyclopentyl*) and (III, R = *cyclopentyl*) reserving for a future communication a fuller study of (II) and (III) and the attempts made

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** *cyclopentyl* and *cyclohexyl* have been expressed by *c.p.* and *c.h.*

to convert them into the lactone (V). We at first found the need for a standard method for the synthesis of acids represented by (I). The Reformatsky reaction of ethyl α -bromosuccinate with *cyclopentanone* as a first stage in the synthesis of α -*cyclopentylsuccinic acid* (I, R = *c.p.*; R' = H) was tried but due to the unsatisfactory nature of the condensation, the method had to be abandoned. A convenient method consisted in condensing *cyclopentyl bromide* with ethyl sodioethane- $\alpha\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate (V) (Bischoff, *Annalen*, 1882, 214, 38) to furnish in good yield ethyl α -*cyclopentylethane- $\alpha\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate* (VI, R = *c.p.*). The latter on hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid,

(V)

(VI, R = *c.p.*, *c.h.*)

followed by decarboxylation, gave α -*cyclopentylsuccinic acid* (I, R = *c.p.*; R' = H). *cycloHexyl bromide* also condensed with (V), in lesser yield, to give ethyl α -*cyclohexylethane- $\alpha\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate* (VI, R = *c.p.*), from which α -*cyclohexylsuccinic acid* (I, R = *c.h.*; R' = H) was obtained. The anhydrides of the two acids have been prepared, and characterised.

Ethyl α -*cyclopentylsuccinate* (I, R = *c.p.*; R' = Et) was reacted with ethyl formate and sodium (Wislicenus, Böklen, Reuthe, *Annalen*, 1908, 363, 347; Carrière, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1922, ix, 17, 42) when ethyl α -aldehydo- α -*cyclopentylsuccinate* (II, R = *c.p.*; R' = Et) was formed in 35% yield. On hydrolysis with dilute hydrochloric acid this was transformed into the original α -*cyclopentylsuccinic acid*. It was found to dissolve in cold alkali, and could be reprecipitated unchanged. It did not give a phenylurethane and was found unchanged after heating in a sealed tube with water at 130° during 3 hours. This latter property is in direct contrast to ethyl formylsuccinate which decomposed under similar circumstances to yield β -aldehydopropionic acid (Wislicenus *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Conversion into β -aldehydo- β -*cyclopentylpropionic acid* (III, R = *c.p.*) (isolated as semicarbazone) was, however, possible on prolonged boiling with dilute oxalic acid (*cf.* Carrière, *loc. cit.*). A trace of copper-bronze was found to facilitate this reaction. A fuller study is being made of these compounds.

In view of the work of Wren and Crawford (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 230) it was considered of interest to resolve the synthesised *dl*- α -*cyclopentylsuccinic acid*. The neutral brucine salt was formed, and resolution effected in the usual way. The *d* and *l* forms had $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +17.81° and $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -16.94° respectively. They melt at 135°, while the *dl*-acid melts at 116-117°.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

cyclopentyl Bromide.—The method indicated by Hiers and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 2389) has been applied for the preparation of this compound. *cyclopentanol* (146 g.) was cooled to -5° under good stirring. Pure phosphorus tribromide (200 g.) was added slowly and care was taken to see that the temperature did not rise above 0° . The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 hours, after which it was gradually raised to 100° and the mixture stirred for 1 hour. On cooling, the product was extracted thrice with petroleum ether, and the extract repeatedly washed with water, dried over anhydrous calcium chloride, and the solvent removed. *cyclopentyl bromide* distilled at $133-34^{\circ}/680$ mm., yield 200 g. (88%). The above method would appear to be by far the best one for the preparation of the bromide.

Ethyl α -cyclopentylethane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate (VI, R=c.p.).—Sodium (28.75 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (400 c.c.) and after cooling ethyl ethane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate (308 g.; b.p. $170-72^{\circ}/27$ mm.; Bischoff. *loc. cit.*) was added gradually, followed by *cyclopentyl bromide* (186 g.). There was no immediate reaction, but it started after $\frac{1}{2}$ hour's heating on a water-bath, with deposition of sodium bromide. The heating was continued for 12-14 hours after which the product was decomposed with a large excess of water. The oily layer (in which the smell of *cyclopentene* was apparent) was taken up in ether, the ethereal solution washed with water, dried and ether removed. The ethereal residue was fractionated in *vacuo*, 25 g. distilled below $165^{\circ}/10$ mm., and the major fraction representing ethyl α -*cyclopentyl*-ethane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate distilled at $165-170^{\circ}/5$ mm. as a colourless oil with feeble odour. On redistillation it had b.p. $166^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 300 g. (75%). (Found: C, 61.0; H, 8.1. $C_{18}H_{26}O_6$ requires C, 61.1; H, 8.3 per cent).

Hydrolysis, followed by Decarboxylation of (VI, R=c.p.) *with Hydrochloric Acid: α -cyclopentylsuccinic Acid* (I, R=c.p.; R'=H).—The above ester (VI, R=c.p.) was mixed with hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19, 400 c.c.); and was refluxed on a sand-bath for 70 hours, a further addition of hydrochloric acid (50 c. c.) being made towards the end of this period. On allowing to cool, α -*cyclopentylsuccinic acid* separated in an almost pure condition. α -*cyclopentylsuccinic acid* crystallises from boiling water in plates, m. p. $116-17^{\circ}$, yield 70 g. It is sparingly soluble in cold water, and easily soluble in the common organic solvents except ligroin. [Found: C, 58.1; H, 7.9; Equiv., 93.8. $C_9H_{14}O_4$ (dibasic) requires C, 58.1; H, 7.5 per cent. Equiv., 93].

Alkaline hydrolysis of (VI, R=c.p.) invariably gave rise to a mixture

of the corresponding tricarboxylic acid (not isolated in pure state) and an ester-acid, m. p., 112° . In this latter compound only two of the ester groups have been hydrolysed. [Found: Equiv., 128.5. $C_{12}H_{18}O_6$ (dibasic) requires Equiv., 129].

Anhydride of α -cyclopentylsuccinic Acid.—The acid (3 g.) was mixed with freshly distilled acetyl chloride (6 c. c.) and warmed on the water-bath for 90 minutes. The excess of acetyl chloride was then removed under vacuum and the residual anhydride distilled. α -cyclopentylsuccinic anhydride boiled at $120-125^{\circ}/3$ mm. ($176^{\circ}/30$ mm.) as a thick oil. (Found: C, 64.0; H, 7.3. $C_9H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 64.3; H, 7.1 per cent).

The *semi-p-toluidide- α -cyclopentylsuccinic acid* was formed on mixing theoretical amounts of the above anhydride and *p*-toluidine in benzene solution. It crystallises in plates from dilute alcohol, m. p. 174° . (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3N$ requires N, 5.1 per cent).

Ethyl α -cyclopentylsuccinate (I, R=c.p.; R'=Et).— α -cyclopentylsuccinic acid (50 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (300 c. c.) and to the solution concentrated sulphuric acid (6.5 c. c.) was added. The mixture was heated under reflux on steam-bath for 6 hours. The major portion of the alcohol was then removed, and the product decomposed with water. The ester that separated was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, water, dried and ether removed. Ethyl α -cyclopentylsuccinate distilled as a colourless thick oil, b. p., $120-125^{\circ}/2-4$ mm. On redistillation it had b. p. $120^{\circ}/2$ mm.; $d_{25}, 1.0303$. (Found: C, 64.2; H, 9.3. $C_{13}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 64.5; H, 9.1 per cent).

Ethyl α -Aldehydo- α -cyclopentylsuccinate (II, R=c.p.; R'=Et). The improved method of Carrière (*loc. cit.*) was adopted for formylation and isolation of the requisite ester. Sodium (7.2 g.) was suspended in anhydrous ether (250 c. c.) and then absolute alcohol (14.4 g.) was added. The product was allowed to stand overnight to ensure complete formation of sodium ethoxide. A mixture of freshly distilled ethyl formate (23 g.) and ethyl α -cyclopentylsuccinate (60 g.) was then added to it when a fairly vigorous reaction set in, subsiding after a few hours. After standing for 3 days, the resulting product was decomposed carefully with 50% sulphuric acid (48 g.) and ice (75 g.). The ethereal layer was separated, and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The total ethereal solution was shaken with 50% potassium carbonate solution (175 c. c. in 3 equal lots). The formyl compound was dissolved in potassium carbonate solution while the unreacted ethyl α -cyclopentylsuccinate remained insoluble. The potassium carbonate extract was acidified cautiously with dilute sulphuric acid. The ester that separated was taken up in ether, the ethereal solution

washed with water, dried, ether removed and the residual oil distilled in vacuum. Ethyl α -aldehydo- α -cyclopentylsuccinate boiled at $150-154^{\circ}/3-5$ mm. as a thick, viscid oil with characteristic odour, yield 23 g. It gave a purple colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. It did not furnish a phenylurethane with phenyl isocyanate. On being shaken with aqueous caustic potash (2 mol. 10%), it dissolved with evolution of heat, but was reprecipitated on acidification (even after one hour's standing). (Found: C, 62.4; H, 8.3. $C_{14}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 62.2; H, 8.15 per cent).

Behaviour of the above Ester with dilute Hydrochloric Acid.—The ester (1 g.) was mixed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 c.c.) and water (8 c.c.) and refluxed on a sand-bath till the ester went into solution. On allowing to cool, a solid was obtained, which after one crystallisation from water, melted at $116-117^{\circ}$. It has been identified as α -cyclopentylsuccinic acid by a mixed melting point determination.

Attempt towards Decarboxylation.—Following Wislicenus *et. al* (*loc. cit.*) the above ester (1 g.) was mixed with water (5 c.c.) and heated in a sealed tube at 130° for 3 hours. On reopening the tube, an oil was obtained, b. p. $145-50^{\circ}/2$ mm., but this was, however, identified as the original ester itself by direct comparison and analysis. (Found: C, 62.3; H, 8.4. $C_{14}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 62.2; H, 8.15 per cent).

β -Aldehydo- β -cyclopentylpropionic Acid.—The ester (II, R=c.p.; R'=Et) described above (4 g.) was suspended in a solution of oxalic acid (3 g.) in water (30 c.c.) and copper-bronze (0.5 g.) added to it. The mixture was heated under reflux for 6 hours, at the end of which the unreacted ester was decanted. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried and ether removed. The residue was treated with semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate in aqueous solution when after a time the semicarbazone separated, yield 0.9 g. The semicarbazone crystallised from dilute alcohol in prisms, m.p. 200° . Analysis reveals that it is the semicarbazone of β -aldehydo- β -cyclopentylpropionic acid. (Found: C, 52.3; H, 7.2. $C_{10}H_{17}O_3N_3$ requires C, 52.8; H, 7.5 per cent). Experiments towards the isolation of this compound in large amounts are in progress.

cycloHexyl Bromide.—The procedure adopted for the preparation of cyclopentyl bromide was followed, b.p. $159-160^{\circ}/680$ mm, yield 143 g. of the bromide (88%) from 100 g. of cyclohexanol and 108 g. of phosphorus tribromide.

Ethyl α -cycloHexylethane- $\alpha\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate (VI, R=c.h.).—The procedure described for the preparation of the *cyclopentyl* analogue was followed: [*cycloHexyl* bromide (109 g.), ethyl ethane- $\alpha\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate (164 g.), sodium (15.3 g.), and alcohol (225 c.c.)]. Ethyl α -*cyclohexyl*-ethane- $\alpha\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate boiled at 150-165°/0.5 mm. Redistillation afforded the pure compound, b.p. 160°/2 mm., yield 56 g. (25 %). The unreacted low boiling fractions consisted of unreacted *cyclohexyl* bromide and ethyl α -*cyclohexylethane- $\alpha\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate*. (Found : C, 61.9 ; H, 8.8. C₁₇H₂₈O₆ requires C, 62.19 ; H, 8.54 per cent).

α -*cycloHexylsuccinic Acid* (I, R=c.h. R'=H).—The above ester (37 g.) was mixed with hydrochloric acid (d 1.19, 112 c.c.) and heated under reflux on a sand-bath. Hydrolysis was slow, and complete decarboxylation took a longer time. After heating for 96 hours, the product was cooled when α -*cyclohexylsuccinic acid* crystallised out, yield 15 g.. It was recrystallised from boiling water in colourless plates, m.p. 145°. It is sparingly soluble in cold water, benzene and chloroform and easily soluble in acetone and alcohol. [Found : C, 59.6 ; H, 8.1 ; Equiv., 99.5. C₁₀H₁₆O₄ (dibasic) requires C, 60.0 ; H, 8.1 per cent. Equiv., 100].

α -*cycloHexylsuccinic Anhydride*.—The above acid (3 g.) was refluxed with freshly distilled acetyl chloride (6 c.c.) on the water-bath for 2½ hours, after which the excess of acetyl chloride was removed in vacuum, and the anhydride distilled. α -*cycloHexylsuccinic anhydride* boils at 150°/4 mm. as a thick oil which solidifies to a crystalline mass, m.p. 42°. (Found : C, 65.7 ; H, 8.2. C₁₀H₁₄O₃ requires C, 65.9 ; H, 7.7 per cent).

The *semi-p-toluidide* of α -*cyclohexylsuccinic acid* was immediately formed on mixing equivalent amounts of *p*-toluidine, and the above anhydride in benzene solution. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 187°. (Found : N, 5.1. C₁₇H₂₃O₃N requires N, 4.8 per cent).

Resolution of dl- α -cycloPentylsuccinic Acid.—*dl- α -cycloPentyl succinic acid* (m.p. 116-117°) (10 g., 1 mol.) was mixed with anhydrous brucine (42.4 g. ; 2 mol.) and the mixture dissolved in boiling water (250 c.c.). The solution was filtered hot and allowed to cool. After standing for a few hours, the solution was concentrated to 150 c.c.. when 45.5 g. of salt were thrown down. In the table on page 113 is given the volume of the solvent (water) at each subsequent crystallisation, and the weight of salt recrystallised.

The brucine salt was decomposed at this stage with ammonia, and the acid liberated had $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 16.53^\circ$ ($l=1$; $c=1.996$ in acetone). To ensure that an acid of maximum rotation was obtained, this acid (2 g.) was again combined with brucine (8.5 g.) in minimum amount of water, when the salt

(1.4 g.) separated. This was recrystallised once from water (25 c.c.) and then decomposed with ammonia and the acid liberated (0.9 g.). It had $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 16.16^\circ$ ($l=1$; $c=1.484$ in acetone). On recrystallisation from water this had $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 17.81^\circ$ ($l=1$; $c=2.348$ in acetone). [Found: Equiv., 93.4. $C_9H_{14}O_4$ (dibasic) requires Equiv., 93.0].

Crystallisation.	Wt. of salt.	Vol. of solvent.
I	45.5 g.	100 c.c.
II	21.2	100
III	20.0	90
IV	14.7	60
V	10.0	50

Isolation of the laevo-isomer.—The parent mother-liquor and mother liquor from (I), (II) and (III) crystallisations were combined together and concentrated *in vacuo* to 200 c.c. ($\frac{1}{2}$ its bulk). The concentrate was cooled to 0° and the solid that separated was filtered. This process was repeated twice and the resulting mother-liquor was decomposed with ammonia and the acid liberated. This had $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 14.06^\circ$ ($l=1$; $c=2.348$ in acetone). This active acid (0.5 g.) was combined with brucine (2.1 g.) in water, the salt that separated was rejected and the active acid was liberated. This was recrystallised from water once, and then it had $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 16.94$ ($l=1$; $c=1.830$ in acetone). [Found: Equiv., 93.6. $C_{19}H_{14}O_4$ (dibasic) requires Equiv., 93.0). Both the above active forms melted at 135° .

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